

**CONFUCIUS'S VISION OF A HARMONIOUS SOCIETY AS AN IMPORTANT
FACTOR IN THE SUCCESSFUL DEVELOPMENT AND PROSPERITY OF THE
STATE AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL****Tian Bo**

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Abstract. Confucius's teachings on a harmonious society remain relevant in the modern global era for several reasons. Confucius' teachings focus on ethics, morality and personal responsibility. In a world plagued by global challenges such as climate change, inequality and conflict, Confucius's principles remain important in shaping human attitudes and behavior. Confucian philosophy insists on achieving social harmony by respecting elders, respecting traditions, and resolving conflicts through dialogue. This can be useful in today's world where there are many cultural and social differences. Many of Confucius's core principles, such as respect for human dignity, justice and honesty, are consistent with universal values that are upheld worldwide.

Keywords: Confucius, morality, educational paradigm, harmonious society, successful development, international level.

Аннотация. Учение Конфуция о гармоничном обществе остается актуальным в современную глобальную эпоху по нескольким причинам. Учение Конфуция сосредотачивается на этике, морали и личной ответственности. В мире, где множество глобальных проблем, таких как изменение климата, неравенство и конфликты, принципы Конфуция остаются важными в формировании человеческих отношений и поведения. Конфуцианская философия настаивает на достижении социальной гармонии путем уважения к старшим, соблюдения традиций и разрешения конфликтов через диалог. Это может быть полезно в современном мире, где существует множество культурных и социальных разногласий. Многие из основных принципов Конфуция, такие как уважение к человеческому достоинству, справедливость и честность, согласуются с универсальными ценностями, которые поддерживаются в мировом масштабе.

Ключевые слова: Конфуций, мораль, образовательная парадигма, гармоничное общество, успешное развитие, международный уровень.

Annotatsiya. Konfutsiyning barkamol jamiyat haqidagi ta'limoti bir necha sabablarga ko'ra zamonaviy global davrda dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Konfutsiy ta'limotida asosiy e'tibor axloq, axloq va shaxsiy javobgarlikka qaratilgan. Iqlim o'zgarishi, tengsizlik va mojarolar kabi global muammolardan qiyalayotgan dunyoda Konfutsiy tamoyillari inson munosabatlari va xulq-atvorini shakllantirishda muhimligicha qolmoqda. Konfutsiy falsafasi kattalarni hurmat qilish, urf-odatlarni hurmat qilish va nizolarni muloqot orqali hal qilish orqali ijtimoiy totuvlikka erishishni talab qiladi. Bu ko'plab madaniy va ijtimoiy tafovutlar mavjud bo'lgan bugungi dunyoda foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Konfutsiyning inson qadr-qimmatini hurmat qilish, adolat va halollik kabi ko'plab asosiy tamoyillari butun dunyoda qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga mos keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Konfutsiy, axloq, tarbiya paradigmasi, barkamol jamiyat, muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanish, xalqaro daraja.

Confucius is the founder of the Chinese Confucian school. In the late spring and Autumn period, as a man with a strong sense of social responsibility, the starting point of his theory is

naturally the construction of social order as a starting point. So Confucius's philosophy, like Socrates's, is largely based on the idea of political ethics over personal morality. From the Analects of Confucius, we can see that he advocated and moralized his ideas and propositions in people's daily behaviors through the rational behaviors of "Returning rites" and "Returning benevolence", to build a "Harmonious but different" harmonious society. The rites developed from the rituals of family sacrifice, family harmony and disciple education since the Yin and Zhou dynasties. This kind of expression in external etiquette rules, in fact, is to rectify the Order of human society. Therefore, facing the phenomenon of "Li collapse", Confucius attached great importance to "Li" as an important means to maintain the old patriarchal hierarchy. He yearned for the perfection of Zhou Li. "Fu Li," he said, "The late king treated people according to the rule of heaven. Those who have lost will die, those who have gained will live... so the world can be reaped and the country can be redeemed." (《Li Ji · Li Yun》) the essence of his "Resuming Li" is to resume Zhou Li, to rectify the changed social reality by Zhou Li, and realize the social order of "Monarch, subject, father, son". Confucius advocated propriety, but he paid more attention to benevolence, "People and not benevolence, how is the propriety?" "Self-restraint and restoration of propriety for Benevolence."

He believed that propriety was based on the "Benevolence" of the monarch, that is, the personal moral cultivation, so he established the moral evaluation system of "Benevolence", regard "For benevolence" as the basis of adjusting social relations and the means of "Resuming rites". He defined the moral meaning of benevolence in many ways. Benevolence can cultivate self: "The teacher's way, loyalty and forgiveness", "Persevering in benevolence, no evil also"; benevolence can help people: "The husband benevolence, they want to stand, they want to reach and reach people", "Bo Shi in the people and can help people"; Benevolence can stabilize the society: "It is also filial piety, and good offenders, rare; not good offenders, but good troublemakers, not also"; Benevolence can also achieve the highest state of life "Die": "People with lofty ideals, no life to harm people, have killed to die". In this way, "Benevolence" has become the highest category of Moral Ethics in Confucius's mind, and has become the criterion for judging value. He also stipulated "Benevolence" from the negative aspect, "Skillful words and color, few carry benevolence", emphasizing that "Benevolence" is not an external form of decoration, but rational internalization and cohesion. At the same time, "Benevolence" should also be regulated by "Courtesy", "Respectful and rude is labor, cautious and rude is anthill, brave and rude is disorderly, straight and rude is hanged. Regarding the essence of benevolence, Confucius thought that filial piety was the root of benevolence, so Confucius not only explained the meaning of benevolence, but also strengthened people's identification with the patriarchal clan ties, to construct the moral emotion based on the family affection, so as to find the psychological basis of order and rules.

It can be said that the whole analects of Confucius is mainly for the "Benevolence" for the notes, and Confucius put the implementation of "Benevolence" into the daily routine of the practice, advocated "Learning while learning.". He also personally opened schools, recruit students, spread his "Benevolence" concept and "Fu Li" idea, for his heart the formation of an ideal society active exploration. However, Confucius's description of differential, stable and orderly, the ideal society is "Harmonious" and not "Harmonious.". Because of the social "Don't", it is difficult to "Orderly", especially in the turbulent era of change, it is more likely to lead to "Ceremony collapse music bad". In order to resolve this contradiction, Confucius put forward the

idea of “Harmony but difference”, which still has practical significance. He holds that “Harmony is the most important part of propriety” and regards “Harmony” as the guiding principle of “Resuming propriety”, then Carry On the adjustment to these differences, causes each to get its own place, finally achieves the overall harmony. At this point, Confucius “Benevolence and propriety” equal emphasis, “Harmonious but different” harmonious society will be completed.

Third, the conception of human civilization.

From Socrates and Confucius's time to modern times, how to maintain the stability, survival and continuity of the society, and maintain the harmonious development of the society, has been a big social problem, and is also a question that many philosophers are keen to explore. From the above analysis of the homogeneity of the two thinkers, we can see that the pursuit of a better and harmonious society embodied in their thoughts, now seems to have more practical significance.

In Socrates's virtuous society, every citizen had virtue. With virtue comes expertise adapted to their job. What he emphasized was the formation of a virtuous society based on knowledge, that is, the construction of a society with knowledge and morality oriented by democracy and justice, this is the meaning of the construction of “Harmonious Society” that we are still exploring today. And Socrates himself for the pursuit of virtue, personal practice of the charm of the personality is precisely the modern people should have a noble character.

In Confucius's quest for a harmonious society, people had their place and each had his place. What he emphasized was the formation of a harmonious society based on individual moral ethics, which was also the essence of his restoration of rites. This “Equal difference” concept and today's “Everyone is equal” legal society is out of place. However, his “Benevolence” as the core of the ethical and moral thought, emphasizing their own moral cultivation, as well as the humanistic care of others, this kind of thought is an important spiritual resource to perfect personality and harmonious society in modern society. And the “Harmony is precious” that he loves most embodies the value idea of Chinese traditional culture. This concept emphasizes “Harmony” and “Neutralization” in dealing with non-essential contradictions, and “Harmony” and “Coordination” in the process of social development, these are reflected in the current “Scientific Outlook on Development” and “Harmonious Society”. In particular, the idea of “Harmony but difference” in dealing with today's complex international affairs, building a “Harmonious world” more positive reality enlightenment.

Tang Yijie, a professor of Peking University and the chief expert of the Confucian Collection Project, put forward the idea of “Harmony but difference” to seek the principle of “Global Ethics”. In his view, “Global Ethics” should be based on the recognition and acceptance of multiculturalism, fully understand and respect the diversity of human civilization, and promote the development of human civilization on the principle of “Harmony but difference”, to achieve peaceful coexistence. If so, this would be Confucius's contribution to humanity.

Of course, Socrates and Confucius's ethical ideas about social order have their limits. Socrates's thought was confined to ethical inquiry, as he overemphasized the search for knowledge as the pursuit of certainty, while equating knowledge with virtuous behaviour and neglecting the discussion of the sociality of such behaviour, that is, how to do it, but lacks in the broader scope theory construction and the moral ethics practice. Confucius put too much emphasis on the relationship between people in society, that is, the hierarchical orientation and adjustment between people, emphasizing the orientation of individuals from the perspective of social stability, and pay little attention to the freedom and reality of individual existence. So much so that from the Han to

the Qing Ruling class were misused as the ideological basis for despotism, to some extent suppressing human development and hindering the overall progress of society. Moreover, Confucius's construction of a harmonious society only focuses on the one-way harmony of the ruling environment, which is quite different from the comprehensive and multi-directional harmony of "Man, society and nature" currently being constructed. In fact, if we combine the ideals of SU and Kong, a stable, orderly and harmonious society full of democracy and justice will emerge, isn't this the "Harmonious Society" we are trying to build today? I think the key reason why their thoughts are still of practical significance after more than 2000 years lies in the human pursuit of eternal values, namely, good harmony and just democracy.

However, the contradiction between ideal and reality is the eternal paradox of philosophers. However, their explorations and pursuits have provided valuable ideological wealth for the construction of a harmonious society and a harmonious world, for the development of human civilization into the eternal spiritual power.

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